

Khirbat al-Fayha

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Also known as: MEGA-Jordan #59331, al-Fehaa, Rujm Ghuweinim, TN10

Coordinates: [31.718316, 35.722917](#)

Periods Attested: Epipaleolithic, Iron Age, Iron Age -> Iron Age II, Iron Age -> Iron Age II -> Iron Age IIA, Iron Age -> Iron Age II -> Iron Age IIB, Modern period, Neolithic

Introduction

Khirbat al-Fayha is located on a hill within the modern village of Fayha, located approximately 6 km west of Madaba, on the western edge of the Madaba Plateau. The site's position on the Fayha promontory, extending west from the Madaba Plateau, affords it accessibility to the arable land of the plateau as well as excellent visibility of the surrounding area. Notably, from Khirbat al-Fayha, the sites of Khirbat al-Mukhayyat and Tall Ma'in are visible. The primary component of the site is a large rectilinear structure dating to the Iron Age II, which is accompanied by a lithic scatter and additional walls surrounding and extending from the summit of the site.

Figure 1. Topographic map of Fayha outlining the rectilinear fort, the cluster of stones, and other wall lines.

History of Excavation/Investigation

Khirbat al-Fayha was first documented by the Department of Antiquities of Jordan in 2013, who registered it as MEGA-Jordan #59331. This report largely focussed on the modern disturbances and threats to the site. Khirbat al-Fayha was similarly noted by the Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East & North Africa (EAMENA) team. In their brief assessment of the Madaba region, the site was noted and described, though solely on the basis of what was visible through satellite imagery (Banks and Zerbini 2015, 28).

In 2022, and again in 2025, the site of Khirbat al-Fayha was visited by the Khirbat al-Mukhayyat Archaeological Project (KMAP), with the goal of formally documenting the site, creating a site plan, conducting a collection of surface material culture, and assessing the preservation of the site in relation to modern disturbances noted previously by the Jordanian Department of Antiquities (Danielson et al. 2025; Danielson et al. forthcoming).

The documentation and mapping of the site revealed several components (Figure 1). Most notable is an approximately 30 by 30 m rectilinear structure on the eastern side of the hill. The external walls of the structure are visible, but the interior walls are largely obscured by rock tumble. A modern cemetery is located atop and within the site, and as such, documentation within was limited. The modern cemetery has contributed significant disturbance to the site, through the burials themselves, and other excavation, including by large machinery. A surface collection of pottery was conducted in the vicinity of the site, with the forms indicating an Iron Age II date—more specifically, predominantly the Iron Age IIB, with some forms dateable to the Iron IIA (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pottery forms from the surface collection at Khirbat al-Fayha.

Approximately 90 m to the northwest of the rectilinear structure was a large cluster of stones, visible from satellite imagery. While no immediate wall lines were apparent, the clustering of stones and their character appear consistent with the interpretation that this cluster originated from a small tower located there in antiquity. Notably, this stone cluster is concentrated at the highest point of the hill, which affords increased visibility to the west. Covering an expansive area in the vicinity of the stone cluster and toward the rectilinear structure to the east, a significant number of lithic artifacts were documented. Preliminary analyses of some of these lithics have tentatively identified them as relating to the Iron Age, Neolithic, and Epipaleolithic periods.

Lastly, surrounding the entire summit of the site is a low wall, deeply embedded in the soil, and with little superstructure, but clearly visible on the surface and from satellite imagery. A secondary documented wall extends downslope to the west, which appears to be associated with water collection.

Discussion

While the modern cemetery atop the rectilinear structure precludes excavation, its interpretation as a small fort seems clear. The regularized nature of the structure identifies it as a planned initiative, presumably by a ruling entity within the highland region of west-central Jordan. The location of the site, as on the western edge of the highlands, and its visibility links with the neighboring contemporary sites at Khirbat al-Mukhayyat and Tall Ma'in, appears to indicate its function: to guard the western edge of the plateau, and to visually link the major settlement of Tall Ma'in with Khirbat al-Mukhayyat. The ceramic data, evidencing activity in the late Iron Age IIA and Iron Age IIB, suggest that the fort may have been constructed in relation to the kingdom-forming events described in the Mesha Inscription (Routledge 2004, 133–53). The walls surrounding the summit of the site and extending westward from it remain poorly understood, though the latter appears to be related to water management. The prehistoric component of the site is likewise significant, though it has only been subjected to preliminary analyses.

Cross Database Link

Levantine Ceramics Project: <https://www.levantineceramics.org/sites/3094-khirbat-al-fayha>

Bibliography

Banks, Rebecca, and Andrea Zerbini. 2015. *The Madaba Ring Road, Jordan: Evidence of Cultural Heritage Assets from Remote Imagery in the Madaba Hinterland*. EAMENA: Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa. University of Oxford.

Routledge, Bruce. 2004. *Moab in the Iron Age: Hegemony, Polity, Archaeology*. University of Pennsylvania Press.

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Site Specific Exhaustive Bibliography

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